

REPRESENTATIONS FOR $\beta(10)$

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ABSTRACT. Here two novel expressions of the Dirichlet Beta function at 10 are provided.

The Dirichlet Beta function is defined by the sum

$$\beta(m) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{(2n-1)^m}, \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \\ m = 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{array} \right\} \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (1)$$

When m are even positive integers, no one knows the defined formula above whether there are/exist closed-form solutions.

As a typical example of $\beta(\text{even})$, $\beta(2)$, commonly appears in the form of infinite series and definite integrals, while other $\beta(4)$, $\beta(6)$, $\beta(8)$ and $\beta(10)$ etc. can rarely be seen.

Obviously, $\beta(10)$ is the fifth one of the Dirichlet Beta function at even. Two novel expressions with infinite series for $\beta(10)$ derived in last year are first shown below (the formulas are a little long, see Appendix for more details)

$$\beta(10) = \pi^9 \left(\frac{12497299839061}{43919715926016000} - \frac{25780953733 \ln 2}{121999210905600} - \frac{1734634309 \ln \pi}{17428458700800} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\left\{ 35458290 + (2n+9) \left[\frac{(11785005) 2^{4n+13}}{+ \square} - (135) 2^{18} \right] \right\} |B_{2n}| \pi^{2n}}{(17729145) 2^{2n+11} n (2n+9)!} \right), \quad (2)$$

and

$$\beta(10) = \pi^9 \left(\frac{8683836877}{25819938816000} - \frac{601631911 \ln 2}{903697858560} + \frac{243 \ln 3}{2293760} + \frac{11659327 \ln \pi}{215166156800} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\left\{ (2n+9) \left[\frac{(3943635) 2^{4n+13}}{- \square} + (15) 2^{18} \right] - (1313270) 3^{2n+9} \right\} |B_{2n}| \pi^{2n}}{(656635) 2^{2n+11} n (2n+9)!} \right), \quad (3)$$

where, B_{2n} are Bernoulli numbers, and

$$\square = (2n+6)(2n+7)(2n+8) 2^{2n} [(10809433) 2^{2n+4} - 24337685],$$

$$\square = (2n+6)(2n+7)(2n+8) 2^{2n} [(50968720) 2^{2n} + 41016827].$$

Comparison of Calculation Results

No	Source (Come from)	Formulas	Value with first 10 terms	Value with first 20 terms
0	$\beta(10)$ is approximately equal to (17 exact decimal digits)		$\beta(10) = 0.999983164026197$	$\beta(10) = 0.999983164026197$
1	Definition	(1)	$\approx 0.999983164026154$	$\approx 0.9999831640261969$
2	in this paper	(2)	$\approx 0.9999750889381567$	$\approx 0.9999827979562427$
3		(3)	$\approx 1.0000451671698933$	$\approx 0.9999860566703379$

Remark:

- (a) The definition expression of $\beta(10)$ converges rapidly;
- (b) Formulae (2) and (3) are for research purposes, not primarily for calculations. Their accuracy increases as the number of series terms increases.
- (c) The red digits in the table above are the exact digits of the every computed value for $\beta(10)$ by comparing to its exact decimal digits.

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Appendix

Formula (2) for $\beta(10)$

$$\beta(10) = \pi^9 \cdot \left[\frac{12497299839061}{43919715926016000} - \frac{1734634309 \ln(\pi)}{17428458700800} - \frac{25780953733 \ln(2)}{121999210905600} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\left[(7 \cdot 18761) \cdot 6 \cdot 45 + \frac{[(26188945) \cdot 2^{4n+13} + 2^{2n} \cdot [(2n+6) \cdot (2n+7) \cdot (2n+8)] \cdot [(10809433) \cdot 2^{2n+4} - 24335768] - (135) \cdot 2^{18}]}{(2n+9)^{-1}} \right] \cdot |B_n| \cdot \pi^{2n}}{945 \cdot (18761) \cdot 2^{2n+11} \cdot n \cdot (2n+9)!} \right]$$

Formula (3) for $\beta(10)$

$$\beta(10) = \pi^9 \cdot \left[\frac{8683836877}{25819938816000} - \frac{601631911 \ln(2)}{903697858560} + \frac{243 \ln(3)}{2293760} + \frac{11659327 \ln(\pi)}{215166156800} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\left[\frac{[(15 \cdot 262909) \cdot 2^{4n+13} - 2^{2n} \cdot (2n+6) \cdot (2n+7) \cdot (2n+8)] \cdot [(50968720) \cdot 2^{2n} + 41016827] + 15 \cdot 2^{18}}{(2n+9)^{-1}} - 70 \cdot (18761) \cdot 3^{2n+9} \right] \cdot |B_n| \cdot \pi^{2n}}{35 \cdot (18761) \cdot 2^{2n+11} \cdot n \cdot (2n+9)!} \right]$$